

The Emerging Role of Emotional Intelligence in the Workplace with Special Reference to IT/ITeS Sector in Chennai City

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 1

Month: September

Year: 2019

P-ISSN: 2320-4168

E-ISSN: 2582-0729

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Majeetha Parveen, SM, and Nirmala Mohan. "The Emerging Role of Emotional Intelligence in the Workplace with Special Reference to IT/ITeS Sector in Chennai City." *Shanlax International Journal of Commerce*, vol. 7, no. S1, 2019, pp. 77–82.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3412492>

S.M.Majeetha Parveen

*Ph.D Full Time Research Scholar, Department of Commerce
Shift-II, Madras Christian College, Chennai, Affiliated to University of Madras*

Dr.Nirmala Mohan

*Associate Professor and Head, Department of Commerce
Shift-II, Madras Christian College, Chennai, Affiliated to University of Madras*

Introduction

Emotional Intelligence is the ability to perceive emotions, to access and generate sentiments to assist thought, understand feelings and psychological knowledge, and to reflectively regulate emotions to promote emotional and intellectual growth.

According to Mayer and Salovey, Emotional Intelligence subsumes inter and intrapersonal intelligence. Inter-personal intelligence is considered the ability to understand other people, what motivates them, how they work, and how to work cooperatively with them. Intra-personal intelligence, on the other hand, is a correlative ability, turned inward. It is the capacity to form an accurate, veridical model of the self and to be able to use that to operate effectively. Social scientists are just beginning to uncover the relationship of emotional intelligence to other phenomena such as leadership, group performance, individual performance, inter-personal or social exchange, managing change, and conducting performance evaluations. According to Goleman, 'Emotional Intelligence, the skills that help people harmonize, should become increasingly valued as a workplace asset in the years to come.'

Emotional Intelligence is a recent behavioural study rising to prominence. It plays a big role in the study of organizational development of the people as it provides a scientific way to understand or assess people's behaviours, attitudes, strengths and weaknesses and interpersonal skills. The term "emotional intelligence" may appear to be a paradox because intelligence is the faculty of thought and reason associated with mind, and emotions are subjective that come from heart, but both are interrelated. Emotional intelligence looks at how people can understand each other more completely by developing an increased awareness of their own and others' emotions. Emotional Intelligence is considered to be a multidimensional form or subset of social intelligence or a form of social literacy.

According to Goleman (1995), Emotional Intelligence “Is a constellation of abilities, skills, and dispositions which, when taken together, can predict a person’s likelihood of future success in several areas, including one’s ultimate niche in society.”The description of the dimensions of emotional intelligence being presented below:

- Self-Awareness - Self-awareness means having a deep understanding of one’s emotions, strengths, weaknesses, needs, and drives. It indicates the ability to recognize understand and accept one’s thoughts, reponses, drives, advantages, and shortcomings as well as to see how these affect other people. People with strong self-awareness are neither overly critical nor unrealistically hopeful. Instead, they are honest with themselves.
- Self-Regulation - Self-Regulation refers to managing and handling impulses, distressing feelings, and upsets rather than denying or repressing these feelings. It implies choosing as to how we express our opinions. Self-Regulation is an on-going inner conversation which helps in staying composed, focused, and calm and helps think even under pressure.
- Self-Motivation - Self-Motivation is an internal state or condition that activates an individual to achieve something. Motivation helps in the achievement of goals. It is an ability to pursue goals with energy and persistence. It provides the drive and the zeal to shape our thoughts and actions.
- Social Awareness - It refers to the ability to put oneself into another’s shoes and look at things or think from his/her point of view. It can be called the foundation skill for all the social competencies. Emotionally balanced people are generally empathetic and not sympathetic.
- Social skills - Social skill is an ability to build rapport with various sections of society and create a network of people. It also refers to the capabilities of handling emotions in relationships well and accurately reading social situations and systems, interacting smoothly, using these skills to persuade, lead, negotiate and settle disputes, for cooperation and teamwork.

Objectives of the Study

- To analyze the level of emotional intelligence of employees in the IT/ITeS sector.
- To test the significant difference among factors of emotional intelligence of employees in the IT/ITeS sector.

Review of Literature

- V. Kalaiarasi, M. Amaravathi, and T. Soniya (2014) attempted to find out the emotional intelligence level of managerial employees and the influence of emotional intelligence on performance. The Analysis revealed that there is a positive relationship between emotional intelligence and job performance. The results indicate that understanding the emotional intelligence level of employees helps to perform the desired outcome. The organization should provide suitable training to the managers and employees to regulate their emotions to help them to achieve the organizational objectives efficiently and effectively.
- Zare Zardeini Hosein and Ahmad Yousefi (2012) investigated the relationship between emotional intelligence and agility of the workforce to determine how indicators of emotional intelligence facilitate the coordination at the individual level. The survey results have shown that psychological intelligence factors have an impact on workforce agility. The results also have revealed that elements which are related to interpersonal competence such as self-awareness, self-control, and self-motivation have more effects on the readiness than factors which are related to social capabilities such as empathy and relationship management. The interpersonal skill also has a more significant role in workforce agility changes.
- Abhiruchi Singh Verma (2013) explored the extent to which software engineers’ emotional adjustment at the workplace is related to emotional intelligence and with its competencies.

The research was carried out in various IT organizations across India. The results of correlation and regression analysis explain that emotional intelligence has a statistically significant relationship with psychological adjustment at the workplace. The positive relationship between emotional intelligence and psychological change at the workplace implies that people with higher emotional intelligence enjoy better relations with peers and superiors; experience working in teams as compared to those with lower emotional intelligence. The reason being high emotional intelligence ensures top motivation, great inspiration level, leadership quality, high negotiation skills, and a pleasant personality. Thus, individuals with more emotional intelligence find themselves in a better position at the workplace irrespective of their place in the organizational ladder.

- Rashmi Bharti and Uma Warriar (2015) aimed to understand the influence of emotional intelligence on balancing work and personal demands of employees. The study concludes that emotional intelligence has a significant relationship with work-life balance. Emotional intelligence seems to help an employee to balance his work and life in a better way. Most often, the employees sacrifice their personal life for their professional growth, and this unequal tradeoff creates work-life imbalance. Emotional intelligence may help them in setting their priorities at the right time, make use of alternative sources of help that bring better balance, be more assertive and learn to say no to unreasonable demands, set realistic goals for self, better team harmony, pride in one's work and makes the employee more approachable.

Hypothesis

- H01: Level of emotional intelligence of employees working in the IT/ITeS sector is equally distributed.
- H02: There is no significant difference among mean rank towards factors of emotional intelligence of employees working in the IT/ITeS sector.

Research Methodology

A research methodology is a way to solve the research problem systematically, and a science of studying how research is done scientifically. The scope of research methodology is broader than that of research methods.

Sampling Techniques

Convenient sampling method adopted for collecting data from the respondents.

Sample Units

In this study, Employees working in various IT/ITeS companies in Chennai approached for collecting data. The companies include TCS, Infosys, Wipro, HCL, Cap Gemini, CTS, SourceHOV, Mphasis, and HP, etc

Sample Size

The Sample Size of the study was 100 respondents.

Statistical Techniques used

- Chi-square test
- Friedman test

Limitations of the study

- Data collected within a short time.
- The sample size was limited to 100 respondents.
- The respondents may behave or give opinions differently at different times because of their psychological temperament, which may affect the research study.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

H01: Level of emotional intelligence of employees working in the IT/ITeS sector is equally distributed.

Chi-square test for goodness of fit for Equality of level of Emotional Intelligence of Employees working in the IT/ITeS sector

Level of Emotional Intelligence	Frequency	Percentage	Chi-square value	P-value
Low	25	25	11.060	0.004**
Moderate	49	49		
High	26	26		
Total	100	100		

Note: ** denotes significant at 1% level

Inference

Since the p-value is less than 0.01, the null hypothesis rejected at 1% level, hence the levels of emotional intelligence of employees working in the IT/ITeS sector aren't equally distributed. Based on percentage, the majority of employees belong to a moderate level. The reason being the innate nature of the work environment of the IT/ITeS sector. Most of the employees of the IT/ITeS sector report problems of depression and stress disorders. Since the IT/ITeS professionals are more achievement-oriented, they do not have much of social life and the time spent with the family is also less. These have a significant relation with emotions and their management.

H02: There is no significant difference among mean rank towards factors of emotional intelligence of employees working in the IT/ITeS sector.

Friedman test for significant differences among mean rank towards factors of emotional intelligence of employees working in the IT/ITeS sector.

Factors of Emotional Intelligence	Mean Rank	Chi-square value	P-value
Self-Awareness	3.24	48.311	<0.001**
Self-Regulation	2.37		
Self-Motivation	2.57		
Social Awareness	3.62		
Social Skills	3.21		

Note: ** denotes significant at 1% level

Inference

Since the p-value is less than 0.01, the null hypothesis rejected at 1% level of significance, hence concluded that there is a significant difference among mean rank towards factors of emotional intelligence of employees working in the IT/ITeS sector. Based on mean rank, social awareness (3.62) is the most crucial factor in emotional intelligence, followed by self-awareness (3.24), social skills (3.21). Social awareness can make the difference between success and failure in social interactions. When we are attentive to emotional cues and listen well to others, unproductive conflicts are reduced and increase the likelihood of mutually beneficial outcomes.

Findings and Conclusion

Findings

- The levels of emotional intelligence of employees working in the IT/ITeS sector aren't equally distributed.
- The majority of employees working in the IT/ITeS sector have a moderate level of emotional intelligence.
- There is a significant difference among mean rank towards factors of emotional intelligence of employees working in the IT/ITeS sector.
- Based on mean rank, social awareness is the essential factor of emotional intelligence.

Conclusion

Emotional Intelligence is the emotional balance and competence that helps to get positive results in personal and professional relations. One who is emotionally civilized and competent has less interpersonal frictions and enjoys better mental and physical health.

The IT industry, characterized by phenomenal and increasingly rapid change. The life expectancy of many IT products is getting less each year, and the price realized for such technology and products continuously fall. Because of the unique set of environmental pressures in the IT industry such as continuous re-engineering, outsourcing, more sophisticated markets requiring more creative and breakthrough technologies on the other hand more demanding customers, more competition, and general information overload, these factors have a negative impact on the well-being of employees and the effectiveness of an organization. To deal with these challenges employees need not only technical skills but other skills commonly known as emotional skills, as explained by Goleman (1998) that the personal and social competencies in Emotional Intelligence (EI) enhance an individual's high technical and functional expertise, and for software engineers Emotional Intelligence (EI) means a balance of professional and emotional considerations to problem-solving scenarios. Goleman (1995) explains that EI is more critical than Intelligent Quotient (IQ) for workplace success. Abhiruchi Singh Verma (2013).

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